

**THE SYSTEM OF IMAGES IN A HISTORICAL NOVEL
(on the example of a novel of "Joan of Arc")**

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Summary: This article elaborates on the image systems of historical workpieces. Actually, when we say an image system, we mean elements in a work piece of art that represents the holistic image of a specific space, time, person, place, and so on. For example, a landscape in Mark Twain's "Joan of Arc" or a scene from the life of villagers is also called an image. The clear personage character of these images, its role in revealing its spirituality is an important artistic tool that ensures the integrity of the form and content of the work. When narrating events with the tongue of an imagery narrator in his novel, Mark Twain acts with an event-protagonist-event principle. However, the subjectivity takes lead in this. It has been proved that he effectively used various details, such as nicknames, to express the spirituality, character and artistic aesthetic function of personage images in the work composition, revealing the nature of the images through their appearance, portraits, speeches, turning the whole history into a living image for the reader.

Keywords and phrases: detail, personage, image, landscape, portrait, character, chronotype, historical novel, the system of images, Mark Twain, Joan of Arc.

Introduction.

It is well known that historical novels play an important role in addressing contemporary problems. Especially if the work is dedicated to the heroism of historical figures, its artistic and aesthetic impact will be more effective in properly

shaping the spirit of patriotism in the younger generation. In this sense, in the context of globalization, there is a growing interest in the image in the best works of world literature, which embodies the preservation of national identity, a mature example of universal values. This poses a task for literary scholars to study the system of images in historical work. In this case, it is expedient to focus on works that constitute the mature examples of world literature. Therefore, Mark Twain's historical novel Joan of Arc was taken as a study object. The main purpose of this is to study the characters in the novel as a whole system of events in a specific space and time, and thus to demonstrate the younger generation the logical connection between an individual and the society.

Materials and methods.

One of the traditional methods of examining the system of images in historical works is the application of methods of comparative-typological and structural analysis of the work. But in this case, opinions expressed by scientists at the time also serve to determine the main direction. In particular, scientists refer to the following theory about a problem: "Artistic reality consists of the entire images (object, event, place, etc.) that make it up. Because all characters in the system of images are inextricably linked with each other, they complement, interpret and clarify each other" [4, 206]. Indeed, the depiction of a place in a novel, the landscape, and the character in it all together determine the relationship between two characters and their place in the novel's composition, or a portrait or event image (e.g., battlefield) represents a holistic process along with another event image in the plotline. Apparently, the writer describes the event that took place through a clear depiction of space in the unity of time and space. In this case, if the landscape and the event in it are perceived as separate images, the semantic effect is weakened, it loses its quality as a whole and becomes a part. If described as a system, the plot line of a work of art takes on a more impressive appearance.

Edmond Aubrey's mother, for example, conveys the message one evening when she sees three hundred fairies celebrating as they pass by the Holy Tree, singing, dancing, holding each other's hands, and dancing with their feet off the ground. The people get angry and start chasing the fairies, who are led by the priest Fronte. Meanwhile, Joan falls ill with a fever and is unable to go to the rescue of the fairies. The next day, when she got healed, meets with the priest and then began to speak with humility:

“The fairies were to go if they showed themselves to people again, is it not so?”

“Yes, that was it, dear.”

“If a man comes prying into a person’s room at midnight when that person is half-naked, will you be so unjust as to say that that person is showing himself to that man?”

“Well – no.” The good priest looked a little troubled and uneasy when he said it. “Is a sin, anyway, even if one did not intend to commit it?”

Père Fronte threw up his hands and cried out: “Oh, my poor little child, I see all my fault,” and he drew her to his side and put an arm around her and tried to make his peace with her, but her temper was so high that she could not get it down right away, but buried her head against her breast and broke out crying and said: “Then the fairies committed no sin, for there was no intention to commit one, they did not know that any one was by; and because they were little creatures and could not speak for themselves and say the law was against the intention, not against the innocent act, because they had no friend to think that simple thing for them and say it, they have been sent away from their home forever, and it was wrong, wrong to do it!” [1, 20]

The event in the quoted passage generally represents the lives of the people in Domrémy, which is a small image of the human society of that period. It shows people's worldview, religious bigotry and illiteracy. It is also a time when

Christianity is completely subjugating the peoples' minds, their thinking to their own beliefs, and the pre-Christian animistic worldview is being rejected. However, the fact that the first religious forms of thought, such as the totem (relative to the tree) and the anima (fairies), which lived in ancient French thought, live in the passage, in contrast to Christian philosophy and the concept of struggle, shows that the minds of the people are not yet developed. The spiritual image of the environment in which Joan of Arc was born and raised is fully depicted.

No direct connection between Edmond Aubrey's mother and Joan of Arc as one of the initiators of the conversation can be seen. However, these two characters are connected by the image of fairies. Moreover, it was also this woman who activated the situation, which escalated into a second incident in which an elderly priest punished his father by throwing ashes on his head to appease Joan of Arc and apologize to the girl in this way. This event is also considered an image, as in other novels of the author, where adults bow before the sincere world of children. Here we witness the author creating a new image-event without deviating from his traditional image principle.

It is also no coincidence that the image taken in the above passage - Edmond Aubrey's mother - was inadvertently walking around and saying different things. So, stating that the character of this woman passionately loves surprises, self-expression, boasting and curiosity, the author reiterates that her son has the same nature:

"Now that is certainly a lie, for it runs counter to our Salic law, and so is not legal and cannot have effect", said Edmond Aubrey, called the Paladin, because of the armies he was always going to eat up someday. [1, 34] His mother is also rumored to be chasing the fairies unexpectedly. Until then, people did not take such statements so seriously.

Particular attention should be paid to the nickname Paladin in the quoted passage, as Paladins are in fact French national heroes. Thus, the writer draws

attention to the special place of this image in the work. Just as the Paladin walks next to Charlemagne, Edmond Aubrey, nicknamed the Paladin, was appointed a public flag-bearer when Joan of Arc becomes a commander. [1,131]

In the incident involving Etienne Rose carrying a black flag, the writer tried to address a serious problem. [1, 33-34]. It refers to a shameful treaty concluded in 1420 in Troyes, France, between England and France. According to the shameful treaty, King Henry V of England marries a French queen (daughter of the old King Charles VI) and after his death, the French throne passes to King Henry V of England. The French national society would not agree to such a shameful situation. In practice, however, it was stern Princess Isabella of Bavaria who took over the reins of the country, by cutting off Carl from politics claiming that he had lost his mind. It is a reflection of the problem of national pride, independence, freedom through the eyes of children.

As the boy ascended to the bloody places on their hillside in the woods, he stabbed the stalk of the flag to the ground and said, “There! Stand there and represent France while I get my breath. She needs no other flag now.”) [1, 33]. Etienne Rose speaks passionately to demonstrate the tragedy that befell France.

The author makes it clear in the language of Etienne, nicknamed the Sunflower, with the phrases "There! Stand right there," "represent".

It is through the detail-image of the flag that expresses the idea of French freedom. After these words, the children, who had been waiting anxiously for Etienne Rose to climb up the hill, made a noise and breathed their last, “as if one had announced a death”. The weight of the figurative expression used by the writer to express the mental state of the children was sufficient to assess their mood and situation. The author uses parables to describe the thirst for life (children’s longing) and the horror of death. The semantic contradiction embedded in the narrative from the first page of the novel emerges here once again.

Before that, it had appeared partially in various positions. But in here now it emerges as a clear situation and a collision of cold news. At first, the bad news makes the children a little confused. But Etienne's comments and Jacques of Arc (Joan's brother) like "But many reports come that are not true. Nothing so shameful as this has ever come before, nothing that cuts so deep, nothing that has dragged France so low; therefore, there is hope that this tale is but another idle rumor. Where did you get it?" [1, 35] indicates that the younger generation has hope. This means that patriotism is strong among children, they feel responsible for the freedom of the country. They began to seriously verify the news. Here the author gives a picture of Joan: "The color went out of her sister Joan's face. She dreaded the answer; and her instinct was right". ("Jacques' sister Joan was upset, she was afraid of the answer, her feelings didn't deceive her").

Here, from the narrator's language, Joan is shown to have the ability to anticipate events. In response, a priest from the neighboring village of Maxelle is mentioned. Joan then expresses in front of everyone her terrible words against this very priest. As the writer describes the events, all the images and figurative expressions serve to reveal the images of Joan of Arc's environment, the society in which she was developed as an individual, the people around her. The general form of the interconnectedness of the various images is directed to a single image, i.e. the artistic expression of Joan of Arc. This shows that the system of events in the novel, that is, the system of images, is built chronologically, from simplicity to complexity.

"It is known that there are specific complexities and difficulties in creating a historical subject, a historical genre. Writing a piece in this direction requires great talent and deep knowledge – the ability to deeply analyze the dialectics of history" [6, 16]. According to the dialectics of history, however, events move from particular to general. That is, while the author states from the beginning of the novel that Doremy children are sincere, selfless, patriotic, strong in faith, and have some

mystical views, he slowly leads the reader into real historical events. Such tragic days are partially mentioned in the narration at the beginning of the work in connection with Louis's family and later highlighted by detail-images such as the fugitive warrior, who came in the evening, the black flag. The children who returned to the village after the flag event will now witness the historical and political event that directly affects their village and their lives. As a result, the narration now uses details, linguistic units, and symbolic expressions to indicate this. For example, the image of Edmond Aubrey, nicknamed Paladin, the name of national heroes. The black flag brought by Etienne, as an impressive detail, expressed the extreme of disaster. Here is an indication of the fact that Paladin later, more precisely seven years later, entered the city of Troyes, exactly behind Joan, carrying the flag of the army under her command. Then he was a flag-bearer. Now, feeling that dark days are upon France, he tells the children the story of Troy in pain. But they don't trust him. Because in their hearts the children like Jacques of Arc, Jean of Arc, Pierre of Arc, Joan of Arc, Ometta, Etienne Rose, Mary Dupont, Cecile Letenier, Noel Rainguesson, Edmond Aubrey, Pierre Morel, had trust in King Charles of France, a patriotic love and hope that a miracle would happen and the ongoing tragedy in the country would end. They live with vivid fantasies about national heroes and could not accept Étienne Roze's painful news. But he was telling the truth. In this he is likened to the followers of Charlemagne, who founded an independent state of France, and to whom the nickname Paladin is very appropriate. There were also such nicknames of Joan of Arc, which came out of her character and were initially called "Shy Girl", "Patriot", "Beautiful", and "Brave". Étienne Roze, nicknamed "the Sunflower". Because he had yellow hair and a round freckled face. Pierre Morel nicknamed the "Dragon-fly" because his eyes sticking out so and bulging eyelids.

Apparently, the naming of images in this way is aimed at, first of all, revealing their portraits along with one or another aspect of their character. The author

explains the nickname for children in the narrator's language as follows: “All children have nicknames, and we had ours. We got one apiece early, and they stuck to us; but Joan was richer in this matter, for, as time went on, she earned a second, and then a third, and so on, and we gave them to her. First and last, she had as many as half a dozen. Several of these she never lost. Peasant-girls are bashful naturally; but she surpassed the rule so far, and colored so easily, and was so easily embarrassed in the presence of strangers, that we nicknamed her the Bashful. We were all patriots, but she was called the Patriot, because our warmest feeling for our country was cold beside hers. Also, she was called the Beautiful; and this was not merely because of the extraordinary beauty of her face and form, but because of the loveliness of her character. These names she kept, and one other — the Brave”. [1, 32]

If one pays attention, the author notes that all the children have nicknames, he remembers that these names remained with them for a lifetime, and Joan came up with new names for herself.

Result and discussion. We can share with a number of our personal generalizations during the discussion on the above issue. Some of Joan's nicknames such as "Beautiful" because of her beautiful face and erect figure, and the fact that peasant's daughters usually are taciturn and shy, has been given the nickname "Shy" because Joan is not devoid of this quality. “We were all patriotic, but because Joan was the most patriotic, we called her ‘Patriot’, and our love for our country was nothing compared to her patriotic feelings,” recalls Louis de Conte. So, all the children were patriotic, on the one hand, it was a natural notion, on the other hand, Joan was more selfless than others since childhood, and her love for the homeland was also strong.

While presenting portrait, character, and images as a whole system, the writer based on the artistic and aesthetic tasks assigned to them, and ensures that these aspects of the character are reflected in the subsequent events of the novel. As these

elements between literary texts are mixed with historical events and become artistic history, the narrator's speech also occupies a worthy place in the single system as a whole figurative speech. As a result, the problem of the image system in the novel is solved positively. In this way, the writer creates events that express the point of view of the characters. However, there are the views of the narrator. In the narrator's narrative style, each image is approached in the spirit of the period. However, as he relives these events in his mind, in some places he forgets the boundaries of time and the past in retelling them, far from the time in which the events take place. The result is that the possibilities of a historical novel are infinite, that it can connect the times. For example, when the narrator tells about Joan, he narrates that her mood has changed over the last year and a half, always sad, but she is not grieved, she thinks a lot, dreams, has a great love for France in her heart. This is where the difference between the period, in which the narrator is narrating the story and the period, in which the event takes place, and at the same time the boundary between them can be seen.

We did not observe such a situation in “Tomaris” by Mirkarim Asim. There is no active involvement of the narrator in the events, and the narrator is not involved as one of the characters in the play. As a result, in Mirkarim Asim's work, the reality seems to prevail over subjectivity. In this case, the writer's position is characterized by objectivity, a correct approach to history, while Mark Twain is led by subjectivity, expressing each event as he understands it. This is evident in the narrator's attitude to the images, his pride in them, and his desire to convey something to the audience. As a result, the reader is constantly imagining the listener of the narrator, who is outside the plot in each image, and in the image system in general. This makes it possible to distinguish between the point of view of the writer and the narrator.

Although in the involvement of Tomaris and Joan in war, the love for homeland served as the main driving force in their defense of the homeland, the

differences in cultural values and religious concepts between the two are evident in one way or another in their portrait and character. For example, in her social status Tomaris was a princess, a tribal leader, and a commander. Joan, on the other hand, in her social status is a peasant girl lacking any knowledge and experience. Tomaris, on the other hand, stands out as an image of princess with certain experience, managerial potential and fighting skills. Joan appears in the image of a girl who has not yet found her place in life, but whose heart is crushed by the tragedies of her homeland, with great aspiration to correct them. But there are similarities in the system of images that represent these two images and their power, which can be seen in their ability to fight an external enemy, unite the people, and win as a commander.

The chronotope, artistic time, space in the system of images also have a special place. In both works, the historical reality is based on the specific motive of the events in the transition from one image to another. For example, in the description of historical events portrayed by Mark Twain, time seems relatively subjective. “If we talk about specific models of time, artistic time is relatively individualized and subjective: each character has a concept of personal time [10, 32]. That is, the children in the novel perceive the passage of time and the events in it based on their personal relationships. As a result, although the integrity of the attitude to the common space is felt behind the thoughts of the images, there are sharp differences in the inner world and worldview of the images. For example, one can see an individual time of the images of Joan and the pro-British priest. While the priest emphasizes that a new era has come under the British rule and that the country is now flourishing, Joan and most of her fellow villagers realize that the tragedy of decades all over France has reached them as well. The inner lifetime of the characters here stems from their reaction to the flow of reality. That is, they comprehend two different concepts of time in two positions on freedom and slavery in France. It is this feature that leads to a more dramatic, more tragic depiction of

the relationship of images in the novel. When it comes to artistic time and the system of images, it is also necessary to talk about artistic space. The artistic space here is also presented in two different forms. The first are the images that make the whole of France a single space, and they understand the vast space that encompasses historical collisions. The second is the images that perceive a small space, which is a certain stratum, more precisely Burgundy and pro-British people, for whom space is narrower than their personal worldview, their understanding. This space is all about their livelihood. Images that understand the macro-space perceive a comprehensive space connecting the country's history and future. Such a contradiction in the writer's system of images represents a common image of forces such as the eternal struggle through two different structures in the text: good and evil, freedom, and aggression.

In fact, the image of life, vitality ranked first in any workpiece. In this novel by Mark Twain too, the event–individual–event principle prevails. But the writer states that “Everything grows and changes, including the universe as a vast space that encompasses the being and seemingly infinite, but it also changes. The creative process is therefore rightly divided into different parts. This ... is reflected in the dynamic growth of the experience and, consequently, in the manifestation of the character aspects of the image” [3, 247], represents the changes in Joan's voice and portrait: “As she said those last words a sudden deep glow shone in her eyes, which I was to see there many times in after-days when the bugles sounded the charge and learn to call it the battle-light. Her breast heaved, and the color rose in her face” [1, 58]. This portrait meant that the important thing was that it was a process that preceded a definite state of mind, and Joan was the first to tell such a state to another person. In fact, no one knows how she said it in a real historical situation. But the writer describes the process artistically as if she had seen it, to ensure that the situation comes to life. But Joan's next speech is the culmination of a general conversation that is considered important in the chain of artistic textures: “But to-

day I know. God has chosen the meanest of His creatures for this work; and by His command, and in His protection, and by His strength, not mine, I am to lead His armies, and win back France, and set the crown upon the head of His servant that is Dauphin and shall be King ” [1,58] .

The incident is said to have taken place in early 1429, before Joan going to the Vaucouleurs castle. The sources also contain the conversation with the content preserved. But they are not talking about the interlocutor. So here the writer has brought the reality closer to the truth through Joan’s tongue. But in A.Levandovskiy’s work, Joan of Arc’s prophecy for the first time is mentioned in the meeting with Captain Bodrikur [5, 10-12]. This meeting has been rewritten based on historical sources, which is much closer to the truth. Because the man who recommended Joan to the governor was her uncle Laxart, who was a historical figure and this happened in real life. Here Joan’s prophecy is first narrated in the language of an official, a distant relative of the future king, a representative of the royal army.

The novel depicts Joan of Arc with Robert de Baudricourt, governor of Vaucouleurs in a large spacious living room with several soldiers from the garrison, including Louis. Janna does not reveal she knows Louis, and when she boldly states her purpose, Robert de Baudricourt wonders if she is sane. The soldiers and Robert laugh loudly when they hear her purposes. At a glance, the foolish wish is spread all over the province by servants, cooks, doorkeepers, armor-bearers. But the sincere image at the beginning of the novel, this statement of a romantic-minded girl, who grew up under the influence of folk songs, was in fact sincere. Here the image of Joan, in its essence, resembles the image of Don Quixote by Miguel Cervantes. He, too, laughs at the fact that he has retained the ability to think, to feel, to think sincerely, correctly, socially, which was given to him by his Creator at birth, and to reveal this to those around him. But indeed Joan’s thoughts as human

qualities were sincere, and the path she followed was the right one, but since the society was spiritually impoverished, sincerity seems ridiculous to them.

The girl does not lose herself, although she is oppressed by such an attitude, she cries in secret, but she does not show her grief to people but demonstrates that she is proud, self-confident.

Conclusion.

1. In this, the writer, through the symbol of Joan, strives to prove that reliance on war and oppression, and devotion to religious life alone, is not the main criterion for the development of society. He warns the American society that everyone should live freely in return for their dreams, aspirations, and labor, and that if the environment is the opposite, even a young girl can prove the spiritual poverty of the whole society or the shortsightedness of ignorant, dogmatic priests. The image of Joan was necessary for the writer to express exactly these intentions.

2. The historical events depicted by the author, the compositional structure of the whole work constitute a holistic image of the period, which in essence represents the characteristics of the two worlds. The first one is, indeed, a historical reality, in which such historical figures existed, and the people have suffered greatly. This is a general image of the real history, a specific period of socio-historical development. The second one is the writer's inner world, which requires a relatively in-depth study. That is, the writer reflected the system of questions, issues, and problems that he had pondered and which had tormented him, through a system of artistic images.

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